

Efficient Lewis acid catalysis of an abiological reaction in a de novo protein scaffold

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Abstract

New enzyme catalysts are usually engineered by repurposing the active sites of natural proteins. Here we show that design and directed evolution can be used to transform a nonnatural, functionally naïve zinc-binding protein into a highly active catalyst for an abiological hetero-Diels-Alder reaction. The artificial metalloenzyme achieves $>10^4$ turnovers per active site, exerts absolute control over reaction pathway and product stereochemistry, and displays a chemical proficiency ($1/K_{TS} = 2.9 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}$) that exceeds all previously characterised Diels-Alderases. These properties capitalise on effective Lewis acid catalysis, a chemical strategy for accelerating Diels-Alder reactions common in the lab but so far unknown in nature. Extension of this approach to other metal ions and other de novo scaffolds may propel the design field in exciting new directions.

Main

The Diels-Alder reaction has found broad application in natural products synthesis, providing rapid access to complex molecular structures through formation of two new σ bonds and up to four contiguous stereocenters¹. Despite its synthetic utility, surprisingly few enzymes have been found to catalyse Diels-Alder reactions in nature²⁻⁵. Most of these were discovered only recently and promote intramolecular cycloadditions in polyketide biosynthesis. Designer catalysts for even more challenging bimolecular reactions that simultaneously control reaction pathway, *endo/exo* ratios, and absolute configuration of the reaction products would therefore be valuable additions to the biocatalytic toolkit. Both catalytic antibodies⁶⁻⁸ and computationally designed enzymes have been produced for several Diels-Alder reactions^{9,10}, often with useful stereoselectivities, but their efficiencies are generally modest, even after extensive laboratory evolution, reflecting their reliance on simple hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic binding for transition-state stabilisation.

Lewis acid catalysis by metal ions, a well-established strategy for accelerating Diels-Alder reactions in the laboratory^{11,12}, could potentially augment the capabilities of these designer catalysts. In previous attempts to combine the advantages of transition metal and enzymatic catalysis for Diels-Alder reactions, ligand-chelated copper(II) ions were incorporated into the binding pockets of several natural protein scaffolds¹³⁻¹⁶. Although these artificial metalloproteins promote the enantioselective addition of cyclopentadiene to azachalcones (35-98% ee), the reactions are slow, with reaction times on the order of several days.

In contrast to natural proteins that have been optimised by natural evolution for a specific purpose, *de novo* protein scaffolds that possess promiscuous binding pockets for metal ions and substrates might be more amenable to functional diversification. Consistent with this hypothesis, we recently transformed a computationally designed zinc-binding peptide into an efficient, enantiospecific metalloesterase¹⁷. Here, we show that MID1_{sc}, a 97-amino-acid-long single-chain version of the same metal interface design^{17,18}, is an equally effective template for generating a highly active and stereoselective enzyme for an abiological hetero-Diels-Alder reaction.

Results and discussion

The target reaction

As our target transformation, we chose the Lewis acid-catalysed reaction of azachalcone **1** with 3-vinylindole **2**. These compounds are common substrates for Diels-Alder reactions, related to natural units present in a variety of natural products. However, when paired, they can proceed via competing Diels-Alder and hetero-Diels-Alder pathways (Fig. 1). The development of a selective biocatalyst that promotes only one of the many possible reaction pathways thus poses a chemically interesting challenge.

DFT calculations suggest that in the absence of Lewis acid, the *endo* transition state (TS1-*endo*, 21.4 kcal/mol) is ambimodal¹⁹, leading to both sets of products (Extended Data Fig. 1a). The inclusion of Zn(II)(HO⁻)(H₂O)₂ in the calculation shifts the cycloaddition from a slow, concerted reaction to a fast, stepwise reaction with a free energy barrier of 10 kcal/mol; the second step favours the *endo* hetero-Diels-Alder product (Extended Data Fig. 1b). Experimentally, **1** and **2** reacted to give cyclohexenes **3** and 3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyrans **4** in a 1:3 ratio in DMSO containing zinc triflate. The product ratio shifted to 1:19 in aqueous buffer containing zinc sulphate (Extended Data Fig. 2a–c). ¹H-NMR analyses of the crude reaction mixtures showed that the *endo* stereoisomer of hetero-Diels-Alder adduct **4** is favoured over the *exo* stereoisomer by a factor of 4.6:1 in DMSO and 18:1 in buffer.

Design and evolution of a novel enzyme catalyst

The starting MID1sc protein did not detectably catalyse any reaction between **1** and **2**. However, Rosetta design²⁰ using DFT-optimized transition state geometries predicted that two mutations, E32L and K68W, located on opposite ends of the binding pocket harbouring the zinc ion, would improve substrate binding and transition-state stabilisation while retaining protein stability. These substitutions replace charged side chains that might hinder substrate binding with neutral groups; Trp68 was additionally expected to shield the relatively open active site from bulk solvent. In fact, introducing these substitutions into MID1sc afforded the enzyme DA0, which exhibited low but detectable activity (approximately 2-fold over background at 5 μM enzyme) and a product profile similar to that observed in the absence of protein (Extended Data Fig. 2c,d).

To increase its catalytic efficacy, DA0 was optimised by laboratory evolution. Eight residues lining the putative substrate-binding site were subjected to cassette mutagenesis, and

the resulting variants were screened spectroscopically for consumption of the azachalcone in the presence of **2** and excess zinc. Based on the recovered sequences, five of these residues were re-randomised using restricted amino acid alphabets and shuffled (Extended Data Fig. 3a; Supplementary Tables 2–3). Screening of the combinatorial library yielded the enzyme DA1, which contained the mutations H35C and I64G and provided detectable activity in cell lysates. This double mutant was subsequently subjected to two consecutive cycles of error-prone PCR, focussed mutagenesis of hot-spot residues, and combinatorial shuffling of beneficial mutations to afford the highly active variant DA7 (Fig. 2a; Extended Data Fig. 3a,b; Supplementary Tables 1–3).

DA7 contains a total of 12 mutations, distributed equally over the N- and C-terminal helix-turn-helix fragments of the starting scaffold (Fig. 2b). They include replacement of His35, a noncoordinating histidine near the metal binding site, by a cysteine, and substitution of His39, one of the original zinc ligands, with a valine. These mutations imply a major change in Zn(II) coordination. Aside from these substitutions, only the two amino acids introduced by computation, Leu32 and Trp68, and the first-round I64G mutation affect residues lining the putative binding pocket. All the other changes are more distant and presumably enhance activity by stabilising the scaffold and/or subtly tuning active site conformations during steps involved in catalysis.

Catalytic properties of the evolved metalloenzyme

The kinetics of the reaction were determined by measuring the dependence of the initial velocity on the concentration of **1** at several fixed concentrations of **2** in the presence of excess Zn(II), which is absolutely required for activity (Fig. 2c; Extended Data Fig. 4e). The steady-state parameters were obtained by globally fitting the data to a sequential binding mechanism. The catalytic rate constant (k_{cat}) was 10 s^{-1} and the Michaelis constants (K_{M}) for **1** and **2** were $82 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ and $160 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$, respectively. Steady-state parameters were similarly obtained for DA0, DA1 and DA4, a fourth-round variant. Over the course of evolution, k_{cat} increased more than 600 fold, while the K_{M} values for **1** and **2** decreased by factors of 12 and 18 (Extended Data Fig. 4b–d; Supplementary Table 4). As a result, the catalytic efficiency of the reaction, given by $k_{\text{cat}}/(K_{\text{M},1} \cdot K_{\text{M},2})$, improved by more than five orders of magnitude (Fig. 2d). These steady-state parameters compare favourably with those reported for a recently discovered Diels–Alderase, isolated from white mulberry, that produces an isoprenylated flavonoid natural product called chalcomoracin via an intermolecular [4+2] cycloaddition.²¹

The second-order rate constant for the reaction of **1** and **2** in aqueous buffer containing zinc sulphate ($k_{\text{buffer}} = 0.027 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) provides a benchmark for DA7's chemical prowess (Extended Data Fig. 4a). Catalytic proficiency²², defined as the ratio $[k_{\text{cat}}/(K_{\text{M},1} \cdot K_{\text{M},2})]/k_{\text{buffer}}$, measures the enzyme's ability to lower the activation barrier of the reaction and represents a lower limit on its affinity for the rate-limiting transition state. The value calculated for DA7, $2.9 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}$, indicates that the evolved metalloenzyme is more proficient than all kinetically characterised Diels-Alderases (Fig. 2e), including other designer enzymes that promote bimolecular Diels-Alder reactions (Supplementary Table 5) and natural enzymes like SpnF^{23,24}, AbyU²⁵ and IccD²⁶, which perform unimolecular [4+2]-cycloadditions in the biosynthesis of insecticidal, antimicrobial and antifungal natural products (Supplementary Table 6). This extraordinary proficiency is due to both high effective molarity ($\text{EM} = k_{\text{cat}}/k_{\text{buffer}}$) and relatively tight binding reflected in the low $K_{\text{M},1}$ and $K_{\text{M},2}$ values.

In addition to being remarkably active, DA7 is highly stereoselective, generating exclusively the *endo* hetero-Diels-Alder product (4*R*,6*R*)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran with >99% enantioselectivity (Fig. 2f). This was not the case for variants from the early rounds of evolution. DA0, for example, preferentially forms the *endo* (4*S*,6*S*)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran isomer, but only with 36% enantioselectivity, and the product additionally contains 5% of the competing *exo* stereoisomers (Extended Data Fig. 2d). Although the transition state and product of the DA7-catalysed reaction are structurally homologous, the enzyme catalyses $>10^4$ turnovers per active site (Extended Data Fig. 4f). As a result, preparative-scale reactions in aqueous buffer at room temperature afforded quantitative conversion of the reactants to the optically pure product, providing a mild and practical alternative to standard chemical synthesis.

Structural and computational characterisation

To understand the molecular changes that enabled the emergence of this proficient metalloenzyme, we crystallised DA7 and determined its structure to 1.5 Å resolution (Fig. 3a; Supplementary Table 7). Like the zinc-binding peptide MID1sc from which it originated, the evolved enzyme is a helical bundle consisting of two helix-turn-helix motifs connected by a flexible linker. As anticipated, though, the H35C and H39V mutations altered the coordination sphere of the catalytic Zn(II) ion (His39, His61, His65 → Cys35, His61, His65) and induced a major conformational change that reduced the crossover angle of the two helix-turn-helix fragments by $>30^\circ$ (Extended Data Fig. 5a–d). This structural rearrangement

created a more enclosed hydrophobic pocket in the core of the bundle to accommodate both diene and dienophile. Because a thiolate is a better Zn(II) ligand than a neutral histidine, the H35C mutation early in evolution likely facilitated emergence of this innovation.

A similar conformational change was observed when we evolved MIDsc into an efficient metalloesterase. In that case, though, rearrangement occurred midway along the evolutionary trajectory and did not require substitution of His35 with a cysteine. Although the final, evolved esterase has a similar overall topology and Zn(II) coordination geometry as DA7, its second helix is longer and, because of a Pro mutation, kinked. Like the starting scaffold, it has no detectable Diels-Alderase activity.

Although we were unable to obtain cocrystals of the protein with either substrates or product, docking calculations and molecular dynamics simulations provided mechanistic insights into DA7 catalysis (Fig. 3b–d). As in the solution reaction, the protein-bound zinc ion activates the azachalcone by chelation, facilitating attack of the 3-vinylindole to generate a zwitterionic intermediate, which rapidly cyclises to the hetero-Diels-Alder product. Consistent with the experimentally observed enantioselectivity, only the transition state leading to the *endo* (4*R*,6*R*)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran product fits in the binding pocket with strong coordination to Zn(II) and without steric clashes. A restrained MD simulation of the transition state complex maintains all these interactions. By contrast, the enantiomeric transition state cannot fit into the binding site and still chelate Zn(II). Restrained simulation of the latter reduces steric clashes at the expense of Zn(II) coordination (Extended Data Fig. 6).

In the transition state leading to the observed product, the N-terminal helix-turn-helix fragment positions the azachalcone via numerous van der Waals contacts and a salt bridge between the guanidinium group of Arg28 and the carboxylate of the diene (Fig. 3b). The dienophile binds against the C-terminal helix-turn-helix fragment, placing its indole ring in a small hydrophobic pocket created by the I64G mutation and its vinyl moiety against the *si* face of **1** (Fig. 3c, Extended Data Fig. 6). The zwitterionic intermediate and flanking transition states are additionally stabilised by a hydrogen bond between the indole NH and the amide side chain of Gln80 (Fig. 3d, Extended Data Fig. 7). This interaction is supported by a small hydrogen bonding network consisting of Gln31 and Tyr84, a residue that appeared late in evolution (Fig. 3d). The efficiency of DA7 can thus be ascribed to a combination of Lewis acid catalysis, enthalpic stabilisation of the transition state by the close-fitting binding pocket, and a strategically placed hydrogen-bonding interaction.

The hypothesis that the carboxylate substituent of **1** forms a salt bridge with Arg28 is supported by the fivefold lower specific activity observed for the unsubstituted azachalcone **5**, which cannot make this interaction (Fig. 4). MD simulations of DA7 further suggested that slight displacement of Met87 at the base of the pyridine binding pocket would enable binding of larger heterodienes. In accord with this prediction, the enzyme accepts isoquinoline derivative **6** as efficiently as the original azachalcone (Fig. 4). In contrast, chalcone **7**, which can only bind Zn(II) in monodentate fashion, is a 10^2 -fold poorer substrate than the isosteric azachalcone **1** (Fig. 4). Replacement of the indole NH in the dienophile with an oxygen is even more deleterious. 3-Vinylbenzofuran (**8**), an isosteric analogue of **2**, is completely inactive (Fig. 4), highlighting the importance of the hydrogen bond between the dienophile and Gln80. A 23-fold reduction in efficiency observed when Gln80 was replaced with alanine reinforces this conclusion (Extended Data Fig. 4e).

Conclusions and prospects

Evolution has provided complete control over reaction pathway and product stereochemistry of an abiological hetero-Diels-Alder reaction. Since we only screened for azachalcone disappearance, both properties emerged spontaneously as activity increased. An important challenge for the future will therefore be to see whether equally effective catalysts can be engineered for the other possible isomers of **3** and **4**. Judging from the product profile observed for DA0, it should be possible to enrich variants capable of stabilising the enantiomeric *endo* hetero-Diels-Alder transition state by monitoring changes in product distribution directly by HPLC. Although reversing the inherent reactivity of this system to produce disfavoured *exo* products or normal electron demand Diels-Alder adducts will likely prove more demanding, computational methods²⁷ should help to design suitable libraries that favour such reaction channels.

In the design of any new enzyme, the choice of an appropriate starting scaffold is a fundamental consideration. Most previous attempts to create such catalysts have focused on recycling pre-existing proteins from nature²⁷⁻²⁹. Our results show that evolutionarily naïve metalloproteins like MID1sc are attractive alternatives. Despite its relatively small size (97 amino acids) and simple structure, this de novo helical bundle was able to successfully harness Lewis acid catalysis to produce the valuable dihydropyran moiety with high efficiency and selectivity. Other Lewis acid-catalysed transformations³⁰ and other de novo

scaffolds³¹ may prove similarly amenable to this approach, providing a new avenue for designing and evolving biocatalysts of value for a variety of non-natural functions.

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Acknowledgments

The authors thank M. Solar and N. Trapp from the Small Molecule Crystallography Centre at ETH Zürich for structure elucidation. They also thank B. Blattmann from the Protein Crystallisation Centre at the University of Zürich, the teams from the Mass Spectrometry service and NMR facility at the Laboratory for Organic Chemistry at ETH Zürich and the staff at the Swiss Light Source at the Paul Scherrer Institute for technical support. This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the ETH Zurich. G.J.-O. acknowledges grants from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCI) co-financed with FEDER funds (RTI2018-099592-B-C22 and RYC-2013-14706) and the Mizutani Foundation for Glycoscience (200077).

Author contributions

D.H., G.J.-O. and K.N.H. conceived the project. G.J.-O. and K.N.H. carried out the computational enzyme design. H.A.B. carried out preliminary experiments. S.S. designed the experimental strategy. S.S. and A.C. selected and tested the initial constructs. S.B. and S.S. evolved and characterised the enzyme and analysed the data. S.B., Y.O., and R.C.H. synthesised the substrates. S.B. performed reaction characterisation, protein and small molecule crystallisation. T.M. crystallised the enzyme and solved its structure. Y.Z. and G.J.-O. performed computational MD simulations and DFT calculations. D.H. supervised the research. D.H., S.B., and K.N.H. wrote the paper with contributions from all the authors.

Competing interests: The authors declare no competing interests.

Figure legends

Fig. 1 | Reaction targeted for catalysis by an artificial zinc metalloenzyme. Azachalcone (**1**) and 3-vinylindole (**2**) can react via competing Diels-Alder and hetero-Diels-Alder pathways to afford cyclohexenes **3** and/or dihydropyrans **4**, respectively. In addition to reaction pathway, an optimal catalyst should control the *endo/exo* ratios and absolute configuration of the reaction products.

Fig. 2 | Directed evolution and biophysical characterisation of DA7. **a**, Reaction of **1** (20 μM) with **2** (250 μM) catalysed by zinc (5 μM , grey), DA0 (0.1 μM , magenta) and DA7 (0.1 μM , orange). **b**, MID1sc model showing the zinc ion (yellow), three coordinating histidines (grey), and mutations suggested by computation (magenta) or acquired during evolution (orange). **c**, Michaelis-Menten plots for the DA7-catalysed reaction of **1** and **2**. Data points were measured at 12.5, 25, 50, 100, and 200 μM azachalcone. **d**, Catalytic efficiency increased 140,000 fold over the course of evolution. Error bars indicate the s.d. between three biological replicates for DA0 and DA7 and the error of the fit for DA1 and DA4. **e**, Double logarithmic plot of effective molarity ($\text{EM} = k_{\text{cat}}/k_{\text{buffer}}$) vs. catalytic proficiency ($1/K_{\text{TS}} = [k_{\text{cat}}/(K_{\text{M},1} \cdot K_{\text{M},2})]/k_{\text{buffer}}$, where K_{TS} is the apparent transition state binding affinity and k_{buffer} is the rate constant for the reaction in the absence of enzyme). DA7 and its precursors are compared with catalytic antibodies (black triangles), and variants of the computationally designed DA_20_00 Diels-Alderase (grey circles). The $1/K_{\text{TS}}$ values observed for the natural enzymes IccD, AbyU and SpnF, which catalyse intramolecular Diels-Alder reactions, are shown as dotted lines. **f**, Chiral HPLC analysis of the hetero-Diels-Alder reaction products obtained in the DA7 (orange) and background (grey) reactions. Inset: X-ray structure of the *endo* (4*R*,6*R*)-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyran isomer produced by DA7.

Fig. 3. | Crystal structure of DA7 and docking model of the rate-limiting Diels-Alder transition state. **a**, Crystal structure of DA7 showing the Zn(II) ion (yellow sphere) and the mutations introduced computationally (magenta) or by evolution (orange). A surface mutation (W16S), introduced for crystallisation, is not shown. **b**, Docking model for the preferred rate-limiting transition state (green). **c**, Cut-away view of the active site showing the tight fit of the heterodiene and dienophile in the binding pocket in the preferred transition

state geometry. **d**, The same model as in **b**, but turned 90° to illustrate the hydrogen bonding network that interacts with the dienophile. Labelled distances are in angstroms.

Fig. 4. | DA7 substrate scope. **a**, Analogues of the heterodiene and dienophile were used to probe reaction mechanism and computationally predicted interactions between substrates and protein. **b**, Rate constants for DA7-catalysed reactions with the substrate analogues were determined using 30 μM heterodiene and 60 μM dienophile, concentrations well below the respective K_M values. Error bars indicate the s.d. for three biological replicates.

Methods

Materials, methods and data characterization for all biological, chemical and computational experiments are described in detail in the Supplementary Information.

Data availability

Structural data obtained by X-ray crystallography were deposited in the Protein Data Base or the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre with the following accession codes: 7BWW (DA7^{W16S}), 6YPI (DA7^{W16G,K58Q,L77R,T78R}), 1972193 (racemic *exo-3*), 1972197 (*4R,6R-endo-4*), 1972198 (*R-(+)*-phenylethylamine phosphate). The data can be accessed free of charge via <https://www.rcsb.org> and <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures/>. All relevant data are either provided in the figures, Extended Data and Supplementary Information or available from the corresponding author upon request.

Additional information

Extended data is available for this paper at xxx.

Supplementary information is available for this paper at xxx.

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